

heated with $K_2S_2O_7$ and fumed with concentrated HCl and complexed with pyridine containing 1 M KCl and $RhCl_3 \cdot xH_2O$, not fused are again in the ratio 2 : 1. Obviously rhodium metal or its hydrated chloride salt when fused with $K_2S_2O_7$ is oxidised to an higher-valent state. The fact that Rh^0/Rh^{III} fused with $K_2S_2O_7$ and fumed with concentrated HCl gave two times the peak height as compared to unfused Rh^{III} solutions, suggests a 4-electron reduction process involving the change from Rh^V to Rh^I . Coulometric analysis of the rhodium solutions at constant potential (-0.55 V) under conditions identical to that of polarography using a PAR 173/179 digital coulometer, is compatible with this finding in that the total number of coulombs obtained from 10 mg of rhodium, i.e. 18.50, in fused Rh^0/Rh^{III} -pyridine complex solution is nearly twice that of the unfused Rh^{III} -pyridine complex solution, i.e. 9.28. It is evident that the number of electrons involved in polarography and in coulometry for the fused Rh is twice that of the unfused rhodium. It is well known⁵ that the reduction of rhodium(III)-pyridine complex involves a two-electron process. Evidently pyrosulphate fusion of Rh^0 or $RhCl_3 \cdot xH_2O$ results in the oxidation to the pentavalent state.

The ESCA binding energies of the metals (given in the experimental section) confirm that the platinum group metals undergo oxidation to higher valent state during fusion with $K_2S_2O_7$. It is known that pyrosulphates on stronger heating decompose to SO_3 and sulphates. Many sulphates begin to decompose at red heat forming metallic oxide or the metal and SO_3 or its decomposition products SO_2 and oxygen, which may be responsible for the oxidation. Formation of the latter is increasingly favoured, the higher the decomposition temperature⁶. In the pyrosulphate fusion, possibly Pt-metal group sulphites, $K[Rh(SO_3)_3]$ are initially formed (qualitatively identified by the green colouration produced when the filter paper moistened with acidified potassium dichromate solution was exposed) and change to $K[RhCl_6]$ on fuming with concentrated HCl.

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Kinetics of Cerium(IV) Oxidation of Salicylidene Aminophenols in Acidic Medium

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THERE are many examples in literature which show that cerium(IV) has been used in oxidative determination in a large number of inorganic and organic compounds, e.g. oxidation of ethanol¹, oxidation of *meso*-2,3-butanediol in nitric acid², oxidation of mandelic, *dl*-malic and lactic acid³, and oxidation of citric and tartaric acid and some sugar such as glucose, fructose and arabinose⁴. But the kinetic study of oxidation of Schiff base, e.g. salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol by cerium(IV) in acidic medium has not been observed so far.

Experimental

The kinetic run was initiated by adding a temperature equilibrated solution of Schiff base (maintained at 40°) to the required amounts of sulphuric acid and cerium(IV) sulphate solution in double-distilled water. The course of reaction was followed by removing aliquot (5 ml) at different time intervals and determining the unreacted cerium(IV) by ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator.

To know the stoichiometry of the reactions between these two Schiff bases with cerium(IV) sulphate separately, the method was adopted as described in the literature⁵. The equivalent of cerium(IV) used per mole of salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol was found to be eight at 40°.

Results and Discussion

Effect of concentration of reactants on reaction rate: The variation in the concentration of Ce^{IV} showed the first order reaction. Straight lines were obtained by plotting $\log [Ce^{IV}]$ vs time separately for each Schiff base and pseudo-first order rate constants (k) were calculated from the slopes of these lines; k value was directly proportional to the concentration of Schiff base. This fact is confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs $1/[Schiff\ base]$. The plots were straight lines which do not pass through origin but leave an intercept on $1/k$ axis. These facts show complex formation between Ce^{IV} and salicylidene *o*-aminophenol, Ce^{IV} and salicylidene *m*-aminophenol separately, which decompose to product in the rate-determining step. The reaction velocity decreases as the concentration of sulphuric acid increases.

From the study of the effect of temperature on reaction rate, energy of activation and entropy of activation have been found to be 12.56 kcal mol⁻¹ and -38.65 e.u. with salicylidene *o*-aminophenol and 12.60 kcal mol⁻¹ and -38.70 e.u. with salicylidene *m*-aminophenol as substrate. The following mechanism explain all the kinetic results :

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Quenching of 3-Methyl-5-phenylpyrazole Cation Fluorescence by Inorganic Anions

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INORGANIC anions have been found to be effective in quenching the fluorescence of many organic compounds and a donor-acceptor interaction has been proposed as the most likely mechanism of quenching¹. These halide ions quench the fluorescence of electron acceptors by acting as donor either in the formation of ground state charge transfer complex² or in the formation of excited state charge transfer complex³⁻⁵. In continuation of our earlier work^{6,7} on pyrazoles and substituted pyrazoles, we have now examined the fluorescence quenching of 3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (MPP) cation by halide and thiocyanate anions.

Experimental

3-Methyl-5-phenylpyrazole was prepared from benzoylacetone and hydrazine hydrate⁸ and purified by repeated recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. The purity of the compound was tested by its constant emission maxima with different

excitation wavelengths. The cation of MPP was produced by the addition of concentrated H₂SO₄. Water used was deionised and distilled from alkaline KMnO₄, and deaerated by passing oxygen-free nitrogen. Potassium chloride, potassium bromide, potassium iodide, potassium thiocyanate (all AnalaR) were used as such. Absorption spectra were recorded with a JASCO UNIDEC-650 spectrophotometer and fluorescence measurements were made with a JASCO FP-550 spectrofluorimeter. Experimental solutions were prepared using concentrated H₂SO₄, potassium sulphate and the quencher ion solution. Sulphuric acid and potassium sulphate as ionic buffer were used because it was found that sulphate ion did not quench the fluorescence⁶. Fixed aliquot of stock solution of MPP in methanol (spectrograde) was added to each experimental solution and the resulting concentration of MPP cation was about 10⁻⁵ M. There was no observable shift in wavelength of the fluorescence spectra of MPP cation upon the addition of quenchers. All fluorescence measurements were made at 315 nm.

Results and Discussion

Quenching constants (K_{sv}) for chloride, bromide, iodide and thiocyanate ions were determined using Stern-Volmer relationship⁹ (1),

$$I_0/I - 1 = K_{sv}[Q] \quad (1)$$

where I_0 and I are fluorescence intensities (uncorrected) at a given wavelength in the absence and presence of a concentration $[Q]$ of the quencher respectively. The plot of I_0/I vs concentration of quencher was perfectly linear in all the cases. The average of K_{sv} values obtained from equation (1) and graphical K_{sv} values agreed well. Table 1 shows the quenching constants for the inorganic anions with their redox potentials¹⁰. The linearity of Stern-Volmer plot shows that only one quenching mechanism is operative¹¹ for the quenching by all anions. There was no change in the absorption spectrum of MPP cation with different concentrations of quencher ion (within the limit of the concentration of the quencher used) when compared with the absorption spectra taken without quencher. This rules out the quenching by ground state complex formation, i.e. static quenching.

In the absence of ground state complex formation, quenching must be either by the charge transfer complex formation in the excited state^{4,12} or by the external heavy atom effect which induces intersystem crossing^{13,14}. If these anions derived their quenching ability from external heavy-atom spin-orbit coupling then the quenching constant might be expected to depend on the square of the atomic spin-orbit coupling parameter¹³ of the heavy atom. This leads to the following predicted order of quenching, I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻ > CNS⁻. The observed order of quenching (Table 1) is I⁻ > CNS⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. This order is different from the spin-orbit coupling parameter but it is the order of redox potentials. Hence

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